

Effects of Class-Wide Peer-Tutoring Strategy on Interest and Performance in Redox Reaction among Secondary School Chemistry Students in Katsina State.

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of class-wide peer-tutoring strategy on interest and performance in redox reaction among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State. Two research objectives, research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design involving pretest posttest control group. The experimental group were taught Redox reaction concept using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy while the control group were taught using lecture method. The population of the study consisted of four thousand, two hundred and sixty eight (4,268) (Male=1933 And Female=2335) Senior Secondary School class two (SS II) chemistry students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Katsina state while the sample of the study consisted of two hundred and four (204) (Male=104 And Female=104) SSII chemistry students from two intact classes using multiple sampling techniques. Two instruments; Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) and Chemistry Interest Scale (CIS) with a reliability coefficients of 0.91 and 0.82 respectively using Cronbach alpha reliability test were used to collect data. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while independent sample t-test and Mann-Whitney u-test were used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Results from the study revealed that students taught using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy performed better and have more interest in the chemistry contents than students taught using lecture method. The study concluded that class-wide peer-tutoring strategy improves students' performance and interest and the study recommended that chemistry teachers should exposed students to student-centered and activity-based methods like the class-wide peer-tutoring strategy.

Keyword: Peer-Tutoring, Class-Wide Peer-Tutoring, Lecture Method, Academic Performance, Interest.

Introduction

The primary responsibility of a classroom teacher is to help students attain maximum achievement in their learning tasks (Aluko, 2008). There are several abilities expected of a teacher in order to achieve this goal. Some of these abilities include the ability of the teacher to use appropriate instructional methods in teaching. Educationists have advocated for switching of the teaching/learning process towards student-centered teaching approaches and teachers are requested to employ innovative teaching strategies that are consistent with these approaches (Duvarci, 2010). Students become active participants during their learning process whereas teachers serves as facilitators in these learning strategies. Active participation on the part of students makes them to develop concrete knowledge which will foster their academic performance. Duvarci (2010) suggested that active students' participation in teaching-learning process serves as a prerequisite for constructive learning.

Thus, when learners are actively involved in learning, meaningful learning takes place (Bhattacharjee, 2015). Some of the teaching strategies that enable students to be active participants in the teaching-learning process may include but not limited to laboratory strategy, cooperative strategy, concept-mapping strategy, individualized strategy, fieldtrip strategy and peer-tutoring strategy. These teaching-learning approaches are better suited for teaching and learning science concepts including chemistry.

Chemistry is one of the very important subjects in Senior Secondary Schools in Nigeria as it is a prerequisite subject to study many science and medical courses like medicine, pharmacy, nursing, medical laboratory, biochemistry, microbiology

as well as engineering courses like petrochemical engineering and biotechnology. Chemistry is the scientific study of the composition, structure, properties, and reactions of matter (Ajayi, Agamber & Angura, 2017). According to the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2007), Chemistry teaching aims to enable students develop interest in chemistry, acquire basic theoretical and practical knowledge and skills, apply skills to meet societal needs of creating employment and wealth, be prepared for further studies in chemistry among others. Ability to achieve these objectives of teaching chemistry requires proper conceptualization of chemistry concepts. This requires appropriate use of instructional strategies that could make students practice chemistry effectively, gain functional knowledge of chemistry concepts, achieve good grades in chemistry and apply the learned concepts in their daily lives as scientists. One of the strategies that come to mind at this point is peer-tutoring.

Peer-tutoring is a teaching strategy where a group of students interact to help one another in learning whereby one student occupies the role of tutor and the other students the role of tutees. Peer-tutoring usually involves the group combination of intelligent learners together with less-intelligent learners in order for the later to catch up (Gunter, Estes & Schwab, 2011). Peer interaction among children is useful in learning new skills, knowledge and solutions to one another's problems by playing, talking, quarreling and sharing ideas. Peer-tutoring has been described as a method of cooperative learning based on the creation of pairs of students with a lopsided relationship. Though, the tutor and tutees do not have equal academic ability but they share a common goal (Moreno & Duran, 2002). This goal must be achieved through a relationship framework organized by the teacher. Peer-tutoring is regarded as an excellent resource for facilitating the mastery of interpersonal competencies. There are various models of peer-tutoring as listed by researchers which include: Cross-age Peer-tutoring (CAPT), Peer-assisted Learning Strategies (PALS), Reciprocal Peer-tutoring(RPT), Same-age Peer-tutoring (SAPT) and Class-wide Peer-tutoring (CWPT) (Ogundola, 2017).

CWPT is a peer-tutoring strategy that involves dividing the whole class into groups of not more than five students with different ability levels. It involves pairing brighter students or fast learners to serve as tutors with less bright or slow learners to serve as the tutees. Students can act as tutors, tutees or both tutors and tutees (Brittany & Jennifer, 2012). Students involved in class-wide peer-tutoring receive immediate feedback from peers without fear. In CWPT, the teacher serves as a facilitator, while giving students the opportunity to have monopoly on their learning. Also, rewards of individual performance depend not only on the performance of individuals but on the collective performance of other peer members. The strategy has been implemented in different educational settings in variety of contents and across a wide range of ages and gender (Maheady & Gard, 2010). Unlike other models of peer-tutoring that has restrictions in age or ability levels, the strength of CWPT makes it a choice to use as treatment in this study. CWPT gives opportunity for the entire class to participate in the process and is suitable for classes with large number of students that will not allow the teacher to give individualized attention to each students as the nature of most of our classes (Horvath, 2011). CWPT enhances the spirit of cooperation, collective problem-solving skills, encourages active participation and interaction and thus, enable students to practice basic academic skills simultaneously (Ihekwoaba, Nzewi, Ifeagwu, Chinweuba-Eze & Nduji, 2020) unlike the lecture method which is a teacher-centered method of teaching that doesn't encourages active participation and interaction.

The lecture method which is just a chalk-talk is one-sided which only seems to favor the teachers as it is a teacher-centered approach to teaching and learning. The researcher observed that, many classrooms in Katsina seems to have been dominated by such lecture method of instruction which does not encourage student-student interaction and this method of teaching has widely been used to implement chemistry curriculum in secondary schools. Adegoke (2011) posited that only hardworking students can benefit from lecture method. There is no doubt that, the dwindling students' performance in chemistry in secondary schools (WAEC, 2015; 2016; 2017; 2018; 2019; 2020 and Kenni, 2020) has been a function of lecture method used in teaching the subject (Sabitu & Francis, 2016; Okey & Omeodu, 2018 and Achor, Otor & Kalu, 2021). It is expedient to look for innovative teaching strategies that will foster spirit of collective effort of students because chemistry requires team effort for scientific discovery and breakthrough and a teaching strategies that will foster their academic performance.

Academic performance is the way and manner students deal with their studies and how they cope with or accomplish different tasks given to them by their teachers, it is the ability to study and remember facts and being able to communicate knowledge verbally or down on paper (Ladan, 2015) and be able to remember these facts in the future. Academic performance is also referred to how well a student is accomplishing his or her tasks and studies but there are certain factors that determine the level and quality of students' academic performance. Techniques for measuring academic performance can be continuous assessment or examinations but there is no general agreement on how best it is measured or tested. Obeka (2010) observed that the teacher plays a very crucial role in the development of performance motive of the learners by providing a conducive environment for learning in and outside the classroom. The factors affecting academic performance include: insufficient manpower, insufficient equipment, peer attitude of students, poor understanding of the concept due to their abstract and difficult

nature, utilization of appropriate methods of teaching, poor quality of school teachers and school location (Josiah, 2012). Similarly, Ali, Tela & Saleh (2020) opined that academic performance is a measurable and observable behavior of a student within a specific period of time that consists of scores obtained by a student in an assessment such as class exercise, class test, mid-semester, mock examination, and end of semester examination. Namale, Upoalkpajor & Ayambir (2021) is of the view that using teaching methods that does not encourage active participation of learners is a contributory factor to poor academic performance of the students. Poopola (2010) stated that academic performance is an expression used to present students' scholastic standing which is a function of various factors such as method of teaching, teachers' qualification, child's home background, school environment, attitude and interest.

Interest is an internal factor that affects students' learning. It is an individual's feelings and liking of a particular object, it is a psychological state where the individual student has the will of engaging in a particular activity. Interest, according to Aggarwal (2010) is the feeling that stimulates an individual to activity without any external influence while Kenni (2019) sees it as focusing of the sense organs on or giving attention to some person, activity, situation or object and classified the factors affecting interest as: personal factors (age, sex, mental health and development, students physical health etc.) and socioeconomic/environmental factors (cultural status, education etc.). Students' interest in learning involves three different activities: a) having interest in a particular subject b) having interest in a particular aspect of that subject and lastly c) having interest in a particular activity in the subject (Christidou, 2011).

The amount of interest an individual has on any activity can be a determinant of the level of his success in that activity. There are two types of interest namely: situational interest and individual interest (Mustafa & Salim, 2012). Situational interest is achieved spontaneously by interacting with the environment while individual interest refers to the relationship of a person to a particular content of a subject and is categorized in to two: feeling-related and value-related. Feeling-related interest is associated with stimulation and enjoyment of a content while value-related interest is associated with the importance and personal significance of the content. It is in line with this motive the researcher investigated the effects of class-wide peer-tutoring strategy on interest and performance among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State.

The main problem for this study is that there have been complaints from the public over the persistently poor performance of secondary school students in science-related subjects (chemistry inclusive) in public examinations such as WAEC and NECO. Chemistry students' poor academic performance has been noted in the West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiners' Reports from 2015 to 2020, summary of the report indicated that there is decline in their performance (Uzezi & Zubairu, 2021). One of the factors that led to the continuous poor students' performance in chemistry is lack of appropriate teaching methods that could facilitate greater interaction between the teacher and the students or students with their peers (Achor, *et al*, 2021) which may cause students to lose interest in chemistry and this problem may affect country's standard in science education, because, chemistry is a pre-requisite subject for many fields such as medicine, biochemistry, pharmacy and so on. Therefore, there is need to adopt a teaching strategy that can facilitate interaction among teachers and students and among students with other students. Also, WAEC results analysis in Katsina State from (2012 – 2021) shows that students' academic performance have been poor.

Table 1: WAEC Results (2012 – 2021) in Katsina State

Year	No of Students	Passed (A1 – C6)	% Pass	Failed (D7 – F9)	% Fail
2012	13, 297	3, 550	26.70	9, 747	73.30
2013	16, 898	2, 674	15.82	14, 224	84.18
2014	20, 141	9, 941	49.40	10, 200	50.60
2015	21, 514	13, 302	61.83	8, 212	38.17
2016	20, 404	7, 790	38.20	12, 614	61.80
2017	21, 717	11, 692	53.47	10, 105	46.53
2018	23, 916	7, 188	30.06	16, 728	69.94
2019	27, 134	11, 850	43.67	15, 464	56.33
2020	27, 050	5, 968	22.10	21, 082	77.90
2021	30, 122	12, 167	40.39	12, 167	59.61

Source (Katsina State Ministry of Education, 2022)

Table 1 shows the WAEC results of chemistry students in Katsina State. It shows that there is persistent failure in the students' academic performance over the years. There is need to investigate methods of teachings that facilitates interaction between

teachers and students and students with their peers which will improve their performance and interest. It is with this opinion that the researcher investigated the effects of class-wide peer-tutoring strategy on interest and performance among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this study are to:

1. Find out the mean academic performance of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State.
2. Find out the mean interest of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered:

1. What is the difference in the mean academic performance score of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State?
2. What is the mean difference in the interest of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State?

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students' academic performance taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students' interest taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State.

Methodology

This study employed a quasi-experimental research design, involving pretest posttest control groups design to investigate the effect of class-wide peer-tutoring strategy interest and performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Katsina State. In this design, intact classes were used for the study, so there is no randomization of the subjects. According to Gall, Borg and Gall as cited in Muhammad and Saleh (2020), quasi experimental design can be used when it is not possible for the researcher to randomly sample the subjects and assign them to treatment groups without disrupting the academic program of the school involved in the study.

The population of this study comprises all Senior Secondary School 2 (SS2) chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance (KZEQA), Katsina State. In this zone, there are twenty five (25) public senior secondary schools with a population of four thousand, two hundred and sixty eight (4,268) SSII chemistry students in which one thousand, nine hundred and thirty three (1,933) were males while two thousand, three hundred and thirty five (2,335) were females (Source: Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, 2023). The population comprises of three Local Government Areas namely Katsina, Kaita and Jibia Local Government Areas.

To select a representative sample for this study, two sampling techniques; cluster and simple random sampling techniques were used. At first stage, a cluster sampling technique was used to assemble the population into two groups that is schools under Katsina local government area as one group and then schools under kaita and Jibia local government area as another group. At the second stage, a simple random sampling technique was used to select one school from each group. At the third stage, the schools selected were randomly assigned into the experimental and control groups by balloting. The names of the two schools was written on a piece of paper, folded and placed in a container. The papers were picked without replacement and placed into two different containers labelled as experimental and control group. One intact class from each group was selected and used for the study. Government Senior Secondary School Kamarawa with a sample size of 100 was selected as the experimental group while Government Secondary School Natsinta with a population of 104 was selected as the control group.

The instruments adopted for data collection in this study are: Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) and Chemistry Interest Scale (CIS). The CPT is a 30-items multiple-choice objectives questions with four (4) options lettered A-D. The items were adapted from WASSCE past examination questions on redox reaction from 2005 to 2020. The topics of Redox Reaction

from which the CPT was adapted are: oxidation, reduction, redox reactions, oxidation number of central elements in some compounds, connection of oxidation numbers with IUPAC name, oxidizing and reducing agents and redox equations. The CIS is a 20-items four-point Likert-scale questionnaire that contains Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The reason for using questionnaire is because factual information is required from different students. According to Saidu (2020), questionnaire is used when factual information is desired through different respondents. The CIS was adapted from Ukor and Isah (2015) and it contains two sections; section A and section B. Section A requested for the respondents' bio-data while section B is the actual likert-scale. The scoring procedure of CIS is as follows; SA = 4; A = 3; D = 2 and SD = 1. This scoring procedure was used because all items on the scale are positive interest items and is in line with Okorie (2015) and Bolu-Steve (2015).

The contents of the instruments (CPT and CIS) were validated by four (4) experts, two in the field of science education, one in the field of chemistry, all from Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Katsina and a chemistry teacher. The initial draft of the instruments was submitted to the experts to ensure that the items were properly constructed in terms of clarity, language usage and are in-line with the ability level of the students. The suggestions and recommendations made by the experts were implemented on the instruments.

The procedure employed for data collection was through administration of the Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) and Chemistry Interest Scale (CIS) to the sampled schools by the researcher. The data collected was processed using SPSS version 23, based on the research questions and hypotheses. Descriptive statistics involving mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. Hypotheses one was tested using t-test independent sample while hypotheses two was tested using Mann-Whitney u-test.

Presentation of Results

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of academic performance score of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method

Treatment	N	Mean	SD	MD
CWPT	81	26.72	5.10	7.27
Lecture	95	19.45	7.78	

In Table 2, students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy had a mean score of 26.72 and a standard deviation of 5.10 while the students taught using lecture method had a mean score of 19.45 and a standard deviation of 7.78. The mean difference of 7.27 was observed between students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. The difference is in favor of the students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring. This answered the research question which sought to find out the difference in the mean academic performance score of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method.

Table 2: Mean difference in the interest of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method

Treatment	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mean Rank Diff
CWPT	81	103.37	8373.00	27.55
Lecture Method	95	75.82	7203.00	

Table 3 shows the difference in mean in the interest of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. The students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy had a mean rank of 103.37 while those taught using lecture method had a mean rank of 75.82. The mean difference observed is 27.55. This difference is in favor of the students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy. This answered the research question which sought to find out the mean difference in the interest of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method.

Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students' academic performance taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method.

Table 4: Independent t-test analysis of academic performance score of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method

Treatment	N	Mean	SD	MD	Df	t-value	p-value	Decision
CWPT	81	26.72	5.10	7.27	174	7.185	0.000	Reject H ₀₁
Lecture Method	95	19.45	7.78					

Table 4 presents the independent t-test analysis of the difference in the academic performance of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. There is significant difference in the academic performance score of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. This is because, the p-value (0.000) obtained for which the null hypothesis was tested is lower than the alpha value (0.05) for which the null hypothesis was tested. Hence, the difference is in favor of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance score of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method is rejected. Students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy performed better than their counterpart taught the same topic using lecture method.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students' interest taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method.

Table 5: Mann-Whitney U-test of students' interest taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method

Treatment	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mean Rank Diff	U-value	P-value	Decision
CWPT	81	103.37	8373.00	27.55	2643.00	0.000	Reject H ₀₂
Lecture Method	95	75.82	7203.00				

Table 5 presents the Mann-Whitney u-test analysis of the difference in the interest of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. The analysis indicated that, there is significant difference in the interest of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. The u-value obtained is 2643 while the p-value is 0.000. The p-value is less than the alpha value for which the null hypothesis was tested. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant difference in the mean difference in the interest of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method is rejected. This means that, students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy had better interest than students taught the same topic using lecture method.

Discussion of Findings

One of the major findings of this study is that, there was significant difference in the academic performance score of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method in favor of those taught using class-wide peer-tutoring. This may be as a result of the fact that class-wide peer-tutoring strategy instructional strategy was peer mediated. This finding agrees with the findings of Olatoye and Adekoya (2009), Adekoya and Olatoye (2010), Sabitu and Francis (2016), Ogundola (2017), Abdurraheem (2017) and Ullah, et al (2018) that peer-tutoring and class-wide peer-tutoring has significant effect on students' academic performance. Many other previous studies conducted on peer-tutoring and class-wide peer-tutoring proved the effectiveness of this method of teaching (Kayode, 2021; Abdurrahman, et al, 2020 and Ihekwoaba, et al, 2020). This method do not only help weak learners achieve instructional objectives but also equip fast learners with teaching skills. The use of this strategy led to faster, more effective students learning outcome than the teacher mediated instructional strategy (Ogunleye & Bamidele, 2014). The findings of this study contradicts with the findings of Anggereini, Budiarti and Sanjaya (2018) who reported that there was no effect of the CWPT model on students creativity. It also contradicts with the findings of Ajewole (2000) who reported that students that were exposed to concept mapping performed significantly better than those exposed to peer-tutoring.

The second major findings of this study is that, there was significant difference in the interest of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. Students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy had better interest than students taught the same topic using lecture method. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Ajayi (2017) who asserted that learners learn best and have more interest by doing not just by sitting and listening. This may be as a result of the fact that the strategy encouraged the students to feel comfortable in expressing their ideas and opinion in open dialogue as their colleagues will not judge them as teachers will do. Students interaction with others and active participation and involvement were major factors in the development of scientific skills (Ogunleye & Bamidele, 2014) which will improve their interest in the subject. The findings of this study contradicts with the findings of Samuel and Obikezie (2022) which concluded that there was no significant difference on interest in chemistry among students taught with laboratory practical work.

Conclusion

In view of the findings of this study, Class-wide peer-tutoring strategy improves chemistry students' academic performance and interest in chemistry.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Chemistry concepts should be taught using strategies or methods like class-wide peer-tutoring that are student-centered and activity-based methods of instruction and also encourage social interaction, active engagement and self-motivation among learners.
2. Since lecture method was found less effective in this study with respect to students' academic performance and interest, teachers should be discouraged from using it in teaching chemistry in secondary schools
3. Chemistry teachers should be encouraged to use class-wide peer-tutoring in teaching chemistry in order to improve students' academic performance and interest.

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